

Current Problems of Rhinosurgery

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Abstract: If you breathe in through your mouth several times and inhale and exhale through your nose, you can feel that you are breathing through your mouth. But the apparent convenience has consequences. Breathing through the nose is important and necessary. Passing through the nasal cavity, the air undergoes mechanical cleaning from dust, allergens and pathogenic microorganisms. The air flow is also heated, which prevents cold air from entering the bronchopulmonary system.

Up to 80% of the total number of patients who consult an otolaryngologist have problems with nasal breathing. It may depend on various factors and it is very important to understand that this problem requires the careful attention of the doctor and the patient. Difficulty in breathing through the nose not only makes it difficult to communicate, exercise and sleep, but can also lead to the development of inflammatory diseases in the sinuses and similar complications. Therefore, if you notice any warning signs, do not forget to consult a doctor. All problems can be solved!

Key words: Causes, symptoms, prevention, treatment, operative, conservative.

Nasal congestion can occur in men and women of any age. The main reasons are:

Nasal injury and nasal septum deformity - nasal septum deviation remains one of the most common reasons for visiting an ENT doctor and accounts for 22.4% of all nasal pathologies. However, the actual prevalence of nasal septal deformity is much higher. This pathology occurs in 58.5-90% of the population, but many people do not know about its existence;

Tumor formation in the sinuses or nasopharynx;

Acute or chronic sinusitis;

acute or chronic rhinitis - nasal breathing disorder during rhinitis can be periodic or constant, can be unilateral or bilateral and is the result of nasal passage obstruction caused by swelling or hyperplasia of the mucous membrane, polyps or pathological secretions can be;

Cysts and polyps;

Foreign bodies entering the nasal passages;

Bacterial and viral infections;

Hypertrophy of the nasal concha;

Choanal atresia (filling of the nasal cavity with connective or bony tissue, which makes breathing through the nose difficult or impossible). Complete bilateral choanal atresia is usually diagnosed immediately after birth, because the child cannot breathe independently through the nose. If the atresia is not complete or unilateral, then the diagnosis of the disease is made in later childhood or in adult patients.

There may be other reasons. Therefore, before starting treatment, it is necessary to find out what caused the difficulty in breathing. You can't just put drops in your nose, wash with solutions or

breathe in "asterisk" - you need to make a diagnosis and receive comprehensive treatment on this basis!

SYMPTOMS

How do you know if you have trouble breathing? In addition to the usual runny nose, both nasal passages stop "breathing" due to the abundance of mucus and swelling, there are other signs of congestion.

Main symptoms:

Shortness of breath - when performing basic physical exercises, bending over, climbing stairs, there is a feeling of lack of air, and the patient begins to breathe through his mouth. Nasal breathing is not enough to "ensure" the delivery of the required amount of oxygen during physical activity. And the man begins to suffocate;

General weakness - the patient does not always feel that he is breathing through his mouth rather than through his nose. Weakness develops due to impaired respiratory function, lack of oxygen;

Feeling of dry mouth - the mucous membrane dries up due to impaired breathing of the nose;

Frequent morning fatigue, chronic lack of sleep - nasal congestion does not disappear at night. The patient also experiences breathing problems during sleep, breathing through the mouth, snoring and apnea (short-term pauses in breathing) may develop. In the morning you feel tired even after 8-10 hours of sleep;

The following types of nasal breathing disorders can be distinguished:

One-Sided (nasal breathing is disturbed through only half of the nose);

Bilateral (both halves of the nose are affected).

Depending on the time of appearance:

Congenital pathologies (for example, congenital anomalies of the structure of the nose);

Acquired diseases (rhinitis, sinusitis, etc.).

Depending on the reason:

traumatic;

allergic;

inflammation;

mechanical and others.

COMPLICATIONS

With nasal congestion, the patient often begins to breathe through the mouth, which disrupts many nasal functions. Possible consequences:

Dryness of the oral mucosa - this can lead to an unpleasant smell, a change in taste and difficulty in chewing;

Hypothermia of the throat and cold air entering the lungs - this can lead to the development of frequent colds, chronic tonsillitis and other serious diseases (bronchitis, etc.);

Entry of pathogenic bacteria into the body - there are no barriers when breathing through the mouth, so bacteria, allergens, as well as large particles of dirt can accumulate on the mucous membrane of the mouth and enter during swallowing.

Over time, nasal congestion causes the body to lack oxygen. Basically, oxygen starvation occurs. Because of this, all organs and systems suffer. There may be problems with the heart, blood vessels, gastrointestinal tract, etc.

DIAGNOSTICS

If nasal congestion occurs, the first thing you should do is an otorhinolaryngologist. The doctor conducts an interview and examination, and based on the results of the initial physical examination, makes a decision on the appointment of the examination.

If there is a lot of green mucus and a runny nose develops, laboratory diagnostics are often performed to identify the pathogen. During the examination, a small amount of pathological content is taken from the mucous membrane (smear) and the ON CLINIC doctor immediately sends the biomaterial to the laboratory technicians. Results are relatively quick.

If there is no pathological discharge, but swelling appears, cytological examination of nasal secretions and allergy tests can be ordered. The otorhinolaryngologist directs the patient to consult an allergist.

If nasal septum deviation, sinusitis or polyps are detected during the examination of the nose, an X-ray or computer tomography of the sinuses is prescribed. If traumatic changes are detected, it is recommended to consult a traumatologist or a plastic surgeon.

CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT METHODS

After the examination, the ENT makes a decision on treatment. According to the instructions, conservative and surgical methods are used.

If rhinitis, sinus inflammation (maxillary sinusitis, frontal sinusitis, sphenoiditis) or other infectious or inflammatory diseases are detected, then conservative treatment is prescribed.

According to the indications, the following are prescribed:

Vasoconstrictor drugs;

Antimicrobial agents;

Decongestants;

Mucolytics and other means that can normalize mucus production and drainage.

A combination of different medications may be prescribed to relieve nasal congestion. There are no universal schemes. In each case, the ENT doctor selects drugs and dosage individually.

As for the physical treatment of nasal congestion, UV therapy and UHF therapy are effective. They allow you to fight various chronic runny noses, quickly go into remission and eliminate congestion. A course of 3-7 procedures allows to normalize the condition of the mucous membrane and respiratory function (if the patient follows all the instructions of the doctor and fully complies with the recommendations for drug treatment).

SURGICAL TREATMENT METHODS

In some cases, conservative therapy does not give the desired result. In such cases, surgical methods are used.

The main indicators of the intervention:

Polyps in the sinuses;

Cystic formations;

Tumor process;

Deviation of the nasal septum;

Hypertrophic rhinitis;

Entry of a foreign body into the nasal cavity.

If benign tumors are detected, the doctor removes the tumor and adjacent tissues that interfere with free nasal breathing. Often they resort to high-tech methods: endoscopic rhinosurgery, use of radio knife or laser technology. There are no visible traces of intervention after such an operation.

If a deviation of the nasal septum is detected, septoplasty is indicated. This operation is aimed at restoring the correct anatomy of the nose, and after that, as a rule, a significant effect is observed. Congestion disappears, nasal breathing is restored. The doctor also has access to bone tissue through an incision inside the nasal cavity, so there are no noticeable scars from septoplasty.

If the patient not only suffers from breathing difficulties, but is also dissatisfied with the aesthetics of the nose, then a combined operation can be performed: septoplasty + rhinoplasty. You can restore the anatomy of the septum, as well as change the shape of the tip of the nose, eliminate the tail, reduce the width of the back, etc.

PREVENTION

Key recommendations:

Timely treatment of all ENT diseases under the supervision of a doctor (even if it is a common runny nose);

Minimization of nasal trauma (nasal trauma is often the cause of congestion);

Minimizing contact with allergens and other substances that destroy the nasal mucosa (swelling of the nose often develops due to allergies, which interferes with free breathing);

Annual medical examination (even if nothing bothers you);

Persistent refusal to use vasoconstrictors, compositions for washing the mucous membrane, etc. will have an addictive effect, and in the future the course of runny nose will be more severe, requiring more complex and long-term treatment.

ON CLINIC has a large otorhinolaryngology department, as well as its Plastic Surgery Center, which performs all types of operations (septoplasty, nasal and paranasal sinus tumors, polyps, sinus cysts and nasopharyngeal cysts, endoscopic operations for the removal of foreign bodies) have sinuses, endoscopic surgery of odontogenic sinusitis, surgical treatment of snoring, rhinoplasty). We help patients regardless of the cause of their breathing difficulties. Make an appointment with an otolaryngologist - we will help you!

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